

THE EFFECT OF OSTRACISM IN THE WORKPLACE ON THE ABSORPTIVE POWER OF KNOWLEDGE AT THE COLLEGE OF ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING TECHNOLOGY IN IRAQ

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Abstract

The research aims to identify the effect of ostracism in the workplace on the absorptive power of knowledge in the College of Electrical Engineering Technology in Iraq. The descriptive analytical method was used, and a questionnaire was designed for the purpose of collecting data, which was distributed to a sample consisting of 225 individuals from the college's employees currently enrolled. The study found that there is an effect of ostracism in the workplace on the absorption power of knowledge. The study recommended the need for the senior management in the college to encourage the spirit of cooperation and knowledge sharing among individuals to increase and develop the college.

Keywords: Ostracism in the Workplace, And the Absorptive Power of Knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

The interest of researchers in organizational behavior has recently shifted from studying desirable work behaviors to undesirable work behaviors, and the reason for this shift is the growing spread of such behaviors in the workplace. In addition to the enormous costs associated with practicing these behaviors. Some employees voluntarily emit some negative behaviors that cause harm to the organization, its employees, or both, which is called anti-work behavior. These behaviors range from simple, such as being late for work and spreading rumors, to severe behaviors, such as stealing, vandalizing property, and withdrawing from one's job.

One of these behaviors is ostracism in the workplace. Ostracism in the workplace creates a very serious problem in the workplace, as the repetition and spread of these behaviors endanger the entity and existence of the organization, especially since there is a percentage of employees ranging between 33-75%, as research indicates, that have already participated. Some forms of anti-work behavior, include ostracism in the workplace, absorbing knowledge and not disclosing it) during their careers, Ostracism in the workplace is also considered an undesirable organizational behavior, which refers to the alliance of several individuals against a single person in an attempt to exclude him from the workplace using all methods. Employees who are vulnerable to ostracism are exposed to a wide range of hostile behavior, ranging from constant

criticism of their work to sarcastic comments and gossip, attacks on political and religious positions and opinions, and even verbal and written threats and acts of physical violence. Ostracism also harms organizations, with dire social, psychological, and economic consequences that affect the individual primarily. This is why ostracism is considered psychological harassment, assault, and psychological murder. It causes hidden pain that can only be seen by its owner, who has been chosen to be the prey of an immoral alliance. What increases the danger of ostracism is that it does not have a specific form that can be easily noticed and then combated, but rather it destroys individuals through its spread as a raging social-psychological fire in the form of hidden tactics of destruction, Ostracism may occur in any workplace and all sectors and institutions, and there are workplaces that attract ostracism more than others, and perhaps the matter is due to the organizational nature of work. The public sector comes at the top of this list and the jobs most exposed to a sense of harassment, as research has indicated, are work. In the field of higher education and scientific research, Based on the above and given the importance of the issue of undesirable work behaviors and their effects on the individual and the organization through job withdrawal; The current study aims to study ostracism in the workplace and its impact on the absorptive power of knowledge towards the organization among employees at the College of Electrical Engineering Technology, The problem of the study can be formulated through the following main question: What is the effect of ostracism in the workplace on the absorptive power of knowledge in the Electrical Engineering Technical College, the sample of the study? The following sub-questions can be derived from:

1. What is the level of ostracism in the workplace in the college studied?
2. What is the level of knowledge absorption power in the investigated college?
3. Is there an influence relationship between ostracism in the workplace and the knowledge absorption power of the rejected college?

The research also seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Identifying the level of ostracism in the workplace among employees at the College of Electrical Engineering Technology.
2. Identifying the extent to which employees at the College of Electrical Engineering Technology practice work behaviors (ostracism in the workplace and the absorptive power of knowledge).
3. Identify the effect of the variable of ostracism in the workplace, with its various dimensions, on the knowledge absorption power in the college under investigation.

The research attempts to test the following hypothesis: There is a statistically significant influence relationship between the dimensions of ostracism in the workplace and the absorption power of knowledge in the college under study.

The First Axis: Ostracism in the workplace...a theoretical introduction

1. Concept of ostracism in the workplace

The workplace has a significant impact not only on employees and their productivity, but also on decisions to leave work or hate the workplace. Ostracism in the workplace means the presence of a work environment that is physically, mentally, and psychologically annoying and destructive to competencies, success, and creativity. A large body of research has linked to the existence of a relationship between workplace ostracism. Work by the employee, productivity, job satisfaction, intentions to leave work, and job withdrawal (physical and psychological) (Hickman, 2019). Organizations are interested in implementing their policies that they have drawn up in advance and are committed to them, especially with regard to seeking loyalty to them. This does not come only in a limited way through the application of unjust laws against working individuals and the use of methods of intimidation and threats. Rather, on the contrary, it may lead to adverse results that could be marred. Ambiguity of employee positions at most levels and the fear that causes ambiguity of positions can be a factor of concern for management and thus force it to practice transferring employees and punishing them in response to their behavior at work within the organization. Some researchers, including (Hitlan et al., 2006), have indicated that using punishment to eliminate undesirable behavior may be useless, and it is important for managers to consider other alternative strategies, including rearranging work, working to diagnose and identify problems, and working to eliminate them. (Gamian-Wilk & Madeja-Bien, 2021) defined ostracism as an individual's perception of himself as being ignored or excluded by others. Indeed, recent studies have indicated that excluding and ignoring individuals has a greater impact on their self-esteem and is more painful than receiving hostile treatment from others (Harvey et al., 2018). Ostracism works to undermine the individual's basic needs for communication and participation with others, and therefore the individual's exclusion and ostracism by others may push him to take action and carry out more extreme actions (Liu & It can happen in different ways, but there are three main types of ostracism in the workplace: physical ostracism, in which the perpetrator of ostracism either physically removes himself or withdraws, or avoids physical proximity and contact with the target (the ostracized person). Social ostracism: in which the source (the perpetrator of the ostracism) is The target (the outcast person) and these two types are close to each other physically or physically, as the perpetrator of the ostracism and the outcast person remain within sight, but he ostracizes his colleagues at work by avoiding eye contact, ignoring interventions, and not speaking to him or listening to him, and it is the most severe type. Ostracism causes pain and harm to the people who are exposed to it (Ferris et al., 2008). There is another type, electronic (digital) ostracism, which occurs when there is interaction with others, through some indirect means of communication, in which ostracized people are excluded from Important emails or memos received by others, or online games, Facebook, WhatsApp groups between employees, etc. (Scott & Duffy, 2015). Many studies, including Robinson et al., (2013), have indicated that ostracism in the workplace has purposeful motives for intentionally harming others and non-purposeful motives. That is, without intention, it happens casually, and (Wu et al., 2011) indicated that feeling ostracized in the workplace will lead to low-quality exchanges between members and affiliates of the organization, while (Xu et al., 2020) defined that ostracism in the

workplace is Emotion, which can arise at any time and during any period of work life, and whose impact varies between individuals. It is worth noting that workplace rejection has its negative emotional essence, accompanied by the phenomenon of collapse, randomness, and general indifference, as a result of a decrease in the desire for work and social relationships. Preena, 2021) that workplace ostracism is a feeling and not necessarily a checklist and signs of ostracism in the workplace can be recognized. If co-workers do things that are not in line with the employee's values, or if the workplace supports practices that are not consistent with what the employee believes in, he may begin In feeling stressed, constant pressure can lead to physical or psychological reactions, and (Chang et al., 2021) views ostracism as organizational avoidance, which - refers to the systematic exclusion of a person from the group of which he or she was a member, while (Al -Atwi, 2017) Ostracism is viewed as social rejection, the desire of a person to form a relationship or alliance with another person, even if this relationship is temporary, while the other party refuses to establish this relationship, even if this rejection is implicit, as for (Zimmerman et al., (2016) believes that one of the forms of ostracism in the workplace is linguistic ostracism, which refers to a situation in which two or more people speak in an ambiguous language that is not understood by those around them, while Koay, (2018) explained the intention to be outside the circle of relationships at work. In general, (Fiset et al., 2017) indicated that ostracism in the workplace occurs when a member within a group or the entire group neglects to take actions that involve another organizational member when it is socially appropriate to do so, and (Yang & Treadway, 2018) explained) This definition is more comprehensive, "as it includes social rejection, neglect, organizational avoidance, and social exclusion." The researcher believes that ostracism in the workplace will result in negative consequences such as dissatisfaction with work, physical illness, depression, revenge, and others. Victims are expected to engage in retaliatory behaviors to regain a sense of fairness, meaning that an employee who experiences high levels of ostracism in the workplace will be more likely to retaliate aggressively against the organization, coworkers, and his or her boss.

2. Characteristics of ostracism in the workplace.

There are many characteristics and advantages of ostracism in the workplace (Haldorai et al., 2020).

- Repetition: Negativity is characterized by repetition. These are negative words and behaviors that, if taken in isolation, can seem worthless, but their repetition and regularity make them destructive. (Haldorai et al.,2020)
- Duration: The standard for the duration of ostracism differs among researchers, some of whom believe that the standard of ostracism is the display of negative behaviors for 6 months, some consider it to be less than a week, and some expect it to be a week or more than that (Haldorai et al., 2020).
- Escalation: refers to the process of gradual development of ostracism's behavior or behavior, which begins with an aggressive behavior or look that is difficult to control or ignore, and ends with events in which psychological violence or even physical assault is used.

- Intent or intention: The function of intention or intent in ostracism is related to whether the negative action or behavior was intended first or to the likely outcome of the action or behavior (Haldorai et al., 2020).
- Disparity in power: Ostracism behavior is formed through unequal power between two individuals, that is, an imbalance in power, one of whom is weak and is the victim and the other is strong and is the aggressor, or (vertical upward and downward ostracism, horizontal ostracism) (Haldorai et al., 2020).

3. Types of ostracism in the workplace.

Ostracism can be divided into three main types (Kwan et al., 2018):

- Physical ostracism: (silent treatment from a colleague, conversations end when you approach, no one will go to lunch with you, your desk is moved for no reason, people leave the room when you enter, people look at you, your name is left in the audience, invitation in meetings, you are turned into a lower paying job) (Kwan et al., 2018).
- Social ostracism: (You are not invited to lunch, meetings happen without your knowledge, major decisions are made without your input, people whisper behind your back, assistants are too busy helping you, your boss skips you and goes directly to your employees, your ideas are rejected immediately, You are blamed by association for others' mistakes (Kwan et al., 2018).
- Cyber Ostracism: (Your requests to connect on social media are ignored, people do not respond to your emails and social media sites, you receive “dislikes” for your comments from your colleagues, you are removed from the friend list, you are not included in the group list, you are reset Your passwords or deleted regularly by the administration, you are not included in learning the new software implemented) (Kwan et al., 2018).

4. Consequences of workplace ostracism.

Workplace ostracism affects employee behavior and leaves behind several consequences, including (Chen & Li, 2019):

- Employee happiness: When an employee is ostracized at work, this drains his positive resources in terms of support from the people around him. Such adverse situations at work enhance his emotional stress. Ostracism is like an invisible energy vampire, it can drain or make the employee angrier. and more vulnerable to attack (Chen & Li, 2019).
- Employee Motivation: Conservation of Resource Theory states that when someone experiences the loss of a resource or is threatened with such loss, they tend to act in ways that protect that resource, so, in other words, to conserve their energy, disengaged employees will put in the minimum amount of work to spend Their day (Chen & Li, 2019). According to Oberai, “When an employee realizes that he or she is being excluded by his or her social work group, he or she cannot look forward to receiving any assistance from it to accomplish his or her job tasks.” How can the company motivate them to go beyond their role (Chen & Li, 2019)?

- Opportunities to use strengths: Job-related opportunities at work often come about because of relationships with others; alienated employees will not have the same opportunities to showcase their strengths. So their contributions are greatly reduced. It is something to consider while evaluating an employee who appears to be performing poorly. Are they getting the same opportunities as others (Chen & Li, 2019)?
- Work resources: This element is not limited to the tools we use only, it includes physical resources such as equipment, and intangible resources, such as information. Without these things, it is impossible to achieve business goals (Chen & Li, 2019). Everything can cause a feeling of By being ostracized at work, from being excluded from group interactions to being excluded from meeting invitations, but the result is the same, the excluded employee loses information - an essential job resource that can help him do his job better.
- Employee confession: “Ostracism does not always come in the form of harassment.” “Organizations that manage a remote workforce, such as field services, are particularly vulnerable to unintentionally alienating remote employees, simply because they are not visible during the day-to-day work at headquarters,” Many managers struggle to give the employee frequent, timely recognition (Chen & Li, 2019).
- Employee health: Employees feeling left out at work not only felt less committed to work, but they also reported more health symptoms, “[Excluded employees] experienced more headaches, back pain, and muscle tension – all physiological signs of stress. They also suffered from Psychological withdrawal. So they are present at work, but they have not fully put their minds into their work” (Chen & Li,2019).
- Work culture: A rigid, hierarchical work culture may ostracize employees who are too informal by their standards. Likewise, introverts are more likely to feel excluded in a workplace dominated by extroverts – especially if they work remotely, and this suggests a lack of effort to ensure an inclusive work environment. It is one of the catalysts that turn work culture into a toxic environment (Chen & Li, 2019).

5. Factors that help reduce ostracism in the workplace.

➤ Factors that help an employee deal with ostracism in the workplace (Samma et al., 2020).

- Employee connection to the phenomenon of ostracism in the workplace: Try not to make any assumptions about why you are treated this way, the reason for their behavior is their treatment of it. The employee's job is to not allow their behavior to detract from how the employee is perceived or how he feels and thinks about himself.”
- Writing down the employee's past experiences: Writing down the experiences in writing creates evidence if you plan to approach HR about this, but also, writing is a good release of all that bottled-up stress and anger.
- Nurturing personal life outside of the work environment: friends. family. Playing sports. hobbies. religion. Each of these provides a protective wall against negativity at work.

➤ **Factors that help the organization deal with ostracism in the workplace. (Samma et al., 2020)**

- Obtain regular and frequent feedback: Personal things like workplace ostracism are difficult to measure based on personal conversations alone, however, a more comprehensive data set can be built through regular anonymous employee surveys.
- Distribute recognition equally: Do not place the burden of employee recognition on management alone, it must be distributed between both parties
- Check for own biases: The team leader frequently assigns critical tasks to team members within the office. This process has hidden biases. This makes her remote employees feel excluded because they are not “there” on site. Taking the time and effort to understand Bias, can help identify and address ostracism at work.

The second axis: The absorptive power of knowledge...a conceptual introduction

1. The concept of the absorptive power of knowledge.

The absorptive power of knowledge is the ability of an organization to identify, absorb, transform, and use external knowledge, research, and practice. In other words, the absorptive power of knowledge is a measure of the rate at which an organization can learn and use scientific, technological or other knowledge that exists outside the organization itself. It is a measure of the ability of organizations to learn (ÇIÇO et al., 2015). (Filippini et al., 2013) saw it as “the company’s ability to recognize the value of new information, assimilate it, and apply it to business ends.” It is studied at the individual, group, corporate, and national levels. The antecedents are prior knowledge (knowledge stocks and knowledge flows) and communication. Studies include the firm's innovation performance, level of ambition, and organizational learning. It has been said that in order to be innovative, an organization must develop its knowledge absorptive power. Pilicita et al., 2021 pointed out the ability that a company has to identify, absorb, and apply external information for commercial purposes. (Rafique et al., 2015) explained the organization's ability to use knowledge from the external environment by 1) recognizing and understanding newly acquired knowledge, 2) assimilating through transformative learning, and 3) using the absorbed knowledge to create new knowledge, as well as achieving... Business results through exploitative learning. Palmié et al., 2015 defined two types of adaptation devices: the ability to scan the external environment for new technology and the ability to integrate new external knowledge into innovation processes. (Romasanta et al., 2022) suggested that the absorptive power of knowledge consists of three gradual elements of knowledge concepts within the organization: recognition of the value contained in externally generated knowledge, assimilation of the organization’s current knowledge base, and application of the collected knowledge base for commercial purposes. Later, many modifications to the model were proposed, as the most important model was the model of (George & Zahra) in 2002, who proposed a framework that includes four stages: acquisition, assimilation, transformation, and application of external information. They combine the dimensions in two pairs: acquisition and assimilation, which are ability. On the use of externally derived knowledge, transfer, and investment as a realization of this potential.

(Ruiz et al., 2020) indicated that it is the force that enables the organization to acquire internal and external knowledge that affects creativity and the organization's adaptation to environmental changes. In addition to benefiting from that knowledge, the absorptive power is one of the dynamic forces that allows organizations to create value and obtain a competitive advantage. Sustainable through external knowledge management. (Ayoubi et al., 2016) listed it as a series of organizational methods that are used to distinguish, assimilate, and apply knowledge. (Di Vaio et al., 2021) emphasizes that it is a set of organizational methods and processes that relate to the organization's ability to acquire, absorb, transform, and invest knowledge to produce organizational dynamic capabilities. (Pellegrini et al., 2020) explained the absorptive power as the ability of individuals, work teams, and thus the organization to distinguish the value of new external information, and strive to acquire and absorb it, transfer it, and invest it in a way that affects the performance of knowledge management, as indicated by (Schniederjans et al., 2020). It represents the organization's ability to understand, absorb, and apply new knowledge acquired from external sources. The researcher believes that the absorptive power of knowledge represents the ability of individuals and work teams, and thus the organization, to distinguish the value of new external information and seek to acquire, absorb, transfer, and invest it in a way that affects the performance of knowledge management. The absorptive power in this way resembles the power to process information, or it is the other side of research and development, which in turn includes there are two aspects: creativity and learning. The researcher also believes that the concept of the absorptive power of knowledge is based on several foundations:

- Not being satisfied with one level of absorptive power, as organizations are the product of their individuals and work teams.
- Focus on multi-dimensionality (acquiring, assimilating, transferring, and investing in new and up-to-date information).
- The results of the organization's possession of absorptive power are at the level of knowledge management performance, not performance in general or creativity, as many studies have done.
- A comprehensive approach to absorptive power by focusing on its introduction, dimensions (processes), and results.

2. Dimensions of the absorptive power of knowledge.

- **Acquisition:** This process refers to the act that deals with obtaining knowledge and making it suitable for use at a later time. The activities of acquiring knowledge are: diagnosing knowledge and then seizing this knowledge, and in the end, it is transformed into perception or sensory perception and made fit for use. The acquisition process is completed. Knowledge comes from various sources, and it can be internal or external. Internal sources of knowledge are represented by knowledge repositories, or through participation in experiences and practices, attendance at conferences and seminars, discussion and dialogue, and communication between work groups or between basic data such as financial and economic data, through which the transfer is made. Knowledge and its transformation from implicit

to explicit and vice versa (Manesh et al., 2020). This results in the creativity of organizational knowledge. As for external sources, they represent the knowledge that the organization obtains from outside its borders, which is represented by attending conferences, hiring consultants, newspapers, magazines, and advertisements on the Internet, collecting data through customers, suppliers, competitors, and all those related to the organization, hiring new employees, and cooperating with other institutions from By creating alliances and forming joint businesses...etc. (Noor et al., 2020).

- **Assimilation:** It is the mechanism and path of human formation of individual experience through the acquisition and representation of the cultural, social, and historical experience as the result of generalized knowledge and methods of actions, and therefore abilities, skills, and moral and ethical rules of behavior. This assimilation takes place throughout a person's life as a result of observation, generalization, decision-making, and specific actions without any relation to how. It occurs or occurs spontaneously or under conditions specific to the formation systems. Assimilation refers to the organization's procedures and operations that allow it to analyze, process, interpret, and understand the information obtained from external sources, as knowledge assimilation depends on the ability of individuals to understand new external information and link it to the current knowledge base. (Manesh et al., 2020). The assimilation scale must measure the ability of individuals to learn and understand new external knowledge. Assimilation is an external activity, so the elements evaluate individuals' understanding and interpretation of new knowledge based on confrontation between external and internal actors. Assimilation also consists of processes through which knowledge is combined. Acquired and already existing prior knowledge. It is described as processes and routines that allow the development of new external information and knowledge that is analyzed, processed, interpreted, understood, internalized, and classified. Effective absorption of knowledge requires effective communication, and effective communication requires shared knowledge, which refers to any qualitative knowledge that is shared within the group. Assimilation is the ability to understand, interpret, realize, and learn from external knowledge, and the factors affecting it include the level of education, diverse background, and organizational structure. , internal communications, and human resources (Noor et al., 2020).
- **Transformation:** Knowledge transformation is a process that requires shifting from individual to collective work through the use of internal documents and bulletins that are compatible with explicit knowledge, as well as the use of training and dialogue methods that are compatible with disseminating tacit knowledge. Knowledge transformation is the process in which individual knowledge is transformed. To organizational knowledge, and in the ideal case, knowledge sharing enables individuals to learn and acquire more knowledge and thus contributes to enhancing employees' skills. Accordingly, knowledge transfer is considered an essential component of knowledge absorptive power and is represented in the processes of transferring and transferring knowledge among employees within the organization. As well as exchanging professional experiences and knowledge in a way that enables employees to perform their work and tasks better and more effectively (Manesh et al., 2020).

Transferring knowledge among employees is important because employees represent the source of both explicit and tacit knowledge, so employees should exchange experiences and knowledge with other employees who need it most in order to accomplish tasks well. Moreover, knowledge transfer should be done with passing time in the right place and at the right time in order to obtain the maximum value of knowledge (Noor et al., 2020). The importance of knowledge transformation can be as follows (Manesh et al., 2020):

- Creating and generating new knowledge that leads to gaining competitive advantage;
- The circulation of knowledge among all individuals ensures its continuity and survival in the organization, and thus it is not lost in the event that some competencies leave.

- Application and investment: The process of applying knowledge refers to actually practicing and implementing knowledge, and is based on the idea that the presence of knowledge alone is not enough, but rather it must be applied to reach the desired goals. This process is the last stage of the management of knowledge and is its primary goal, as knowledge has no value in itself. It is the actual application of it that creates value, and when applying knowledge, it must be taken into account that the applied knowledge is compatible with the activities and tasks of the organization (Manesh et al., 2020)

Based on what was mentioned in the concept and dimensions of the absorptive power of knowledge, we conclude that the ability of organizations to absorb knowledge is a condition expressed by a set of the aforementioned organizational dimensions, represented by (acquisition and assimilation) of external knowledge to transform it into their operations, as for (transfer and investment) of new knowledge through the use of Organizations have methods and strategies that enable them to collect external and internal information to apply it in their operations, and it is possible to use the aforementioned dimensions in order to measure the level of that power for any organization (Noor et al., 2020).

The third axis: the applied and analytical framework

1. Analyze the research hypothesis

There is a statistically significant relationship at the level of 0.05) between ostracism in the workplace (ostracism by supervisors, ostracism by colleagues) and the absorptive power of knowledge (acquisition of knowledge, assimilation of knowledge, conversion of knowledge, investment of knowledge) in the College of Electrical Engineering Technology. This hypothesis was verified by finding Pearson correlation coefficients, as shown in the following table:

Table No. 1: The relationship between ostracism in the workplace and the absorptive power of knowledge.

the relationship between variables	correlation coefficient (Pearson)	Significance level
The relationship between ostracism in the workplace and the absorptive power of knowledge	0.835**	0.000

Table (1) shows that the correlation coefficient is equal to (0.835), and the probability value (Sig. is equal to (000.0), which is less than the significance level (0.05). This indicates the

existence of a direct, statistically significant relationship between ostracism in the workplace and the power of knowledge absorption:

Table No. 2: The relationship between ostracism in the workplace (ostracism by supervisors, ostracism by colleagues) and the absorptive power of knowledge.

the relationship between variables	correlation coefficient (Pearson)	Significance level
Ostracism by supervisors and the absorbing power of knowledge	0.843**	0.000
Ostracism by colleagues and the sucking power of knowledge	0.817**	0.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It is clear from Table No. (2): that there is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of ostracism in the workplace and the absorption power of knowledge in the College of Electrical Engineering Technology.

Table No. 3: The correlation between ostracism in the workplace and the power of knowledge absorption

Dimension	Acquiring knowledge	Absorbing knowledge	Transforming knowledge	Investing Knowledge	absorptive power of knowledge	sig
Ostracism by supervisors	0.865**	0.831**	0.804**	0.803**	0.843**	0.000
Ostracism by colleagues	0.846**	0.801**	0.779**	0.776**	0.817**	0.000
ostracism in the workplace	0.861**	0.821**	0.797**	0.795**	0.835**	0.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It is clear from the previous table that there is a strong and significant correlation between the two dimensions of ostracism in the workplace and the dimensions of the absorptive power of knowledge, which indicates that the two dimensions of ostracism among employees of the College of Electrical Engineering Technology, represented by ostracism in the workplace from supervisors, and ostracism in the workplace from colleagues are linked. A positive relationship with the dimensions of the absorptive power of knowledge. The dimension of ostracism in the workplace from supervisors was higher in correlation (0.843) to the absorptive power of knowledge than the dimension of ostracism in the workplace from co-workers with a correlation coefficient of (0.817), and the correlation coefficients were at a significant level (0.000), and this It indicates that the vocabulary is put into practice despite being exposed to ostracism in the workplace, but they have a high degree of knowledge absorption power and are able to tolerate and accept it, and they always insist on forming social networks, and they face ostracism from supervisors, or from colleagues, in their workplace with a positive mentality. Which leads to an increase in their ability to adapt and adjust to the negative effects they face from exposure to ostracism - that is, those negative effects - because they believe in

their ability to achieve this. Not only that, but they enjoy dealing with new and unpleasant events and tend to overcome hardship and overcome them. This is consistent with what was indicated by the study of (Wang et al., 2014) and the study of (Wanberg & Banas, 2000).

The researcher concludes that the dimension of ostracism in the workplace from supervisors has achieved the highest correlation coefficients with the dimensions of the absorptive power of knowledge. The researcher explains this by the extent of the availability of this dimension in the college under study, as it is the most available dimension of ostracism in the workplace, and this reflects the importance of this dimension. In influencing the knowledge absorption power of their college employees.

Table No. 5: Regression analysis of ostracism in the workplace and the absorptive power of knowledge

Contrast inflation factor	T sig	T	β	Sig F	F	R ²	R	variable	Dependent variable
1.000	0.000	22.689	0.753	0.000	514.801	0.698	0.835	ostracism in the workplace	absorptive power of knowledge

In order to determine the effect between ostracism in the workplace and the absorptive power of knowledge, a simple regression model was used, in which the variable of ostracism in the workplace was considered an explanatory variable for the variable of the absorptive power of knowledge as a dependent variable. The results of the regression model showed that the regression model is significant through the value of (F). The value of (514.801) with a significance of (0.000) is smaller than the level of significance (0.05). The results indicate that the explanatory variable is explained by the value of (R²) of (0.698). The beta value, which explains the relationship between ostracism in the workplace and the power of knowledge absorption, came in at a value of (0.753) with significance. Statistical, as this can be deduced through the value of (T) and the significance associated with it, which means that ostracism increased by (514.801) units of the level of the absorptive power of knowledge. As the table shows the results of the multicollinearity test, the result revealed that the variance inflation factor for the model was (1.000), which is it is smaller than (3), which indicates that there is no multicollinearity problem among the model variables. We can also write the regression equation as follows:

Absorptive power of knowledge = constant (1.033) + workplace ostracism (0.733) + prediction error

CONCLUSIONS

Our study aimed to identify the effect of ostracism in the workplace on the absorptive power of knowledge. It is a relationship of give and take between the parties, but as a result of some circumstances or factors this relationship may become strained and the relationship between them may be severed. The organization must work to preserve its workers to reduce problems affecting... Work progress, where it was found that there is a statistically significant relationship between ostracism in the workplace and the absorptive power of knowledge within the College

of Electrical Engineering Technology, where the correlation coefficient reached (0.835), and this indicates that the vocabulary in application despite being exposed to ostracism in the workplace, but they have a high degree From the absorptive power of knowledge, they become able to bear and accept it, and they always insist on forming social networks, and they face ostracism from supervisors, or from colleagues, in their workplace with a positive mentality, which leads to increasing their ability to adapt and adapt to the negative effects they face from exposure. Not only that, but they also enjoy dealing with new and unpleasant events and tend to push through hardship and overcome it.

In light of the results reached by the current study, and the suggestions provided by previous studies, some recommendations can be made to those in charge of managing the Electrical Engineering Technical College, and provide them with the skills that enable them to overcome the occurrence of ostracism in the workplace that may lead to job withdrawal, and it is suggested The current study makes the following recommendations:

1. Paying attention to creating social networks between nursing staff members and their supervisors, encouraging them to discuss, talk to, and listen to them about the problems they face, and spreading values that do not encourage isolation and ostracism in the workplace. Not only that, but supervisors or co-workers who practice ostracizing behaviors in the workplace must be punished. Because of its negative effects on both employees of the Electrical Engineering Technical College in the field of application.
2. Care must be taken to improve the absorptive power and the ability to restore balance among workers, by organizing more seminars and workshops aimed at developing their skills in dealing with and adapting to stressful social and emotional situations and events, how to deal with unpleasant feelings and encouraging them to take on challenges. And establishing close and safe relationships with others in order to preserve the individual's emotional resources and increase his desire to stay and work at the Technical College, which is reflected in the efficiency of the administrative service provided by that Electrical Engineering Technical College.

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